

MENTAL WORK CAPACITY OF SCHOOLCHILDREN UNDER MODERN LOAD CONDITIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15340469>

Abstract. *The given article discusses the relevant issues of modern pedagogy, characterizing the mental work capacity of schoolchildren under modern educational loads, with the goal of preventing fatigue development in students attending educational institutions.*

Keywords: *schoolchildren, mental work capacity, educational loads, fatigue, overwork.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that work capacity of a person, the ability to develop maximum energy while spending it efficiently, achieving the set goal with high-quality execution of mental or predominantly physical work, is ensured by the optimal condition of the functions of various physiological systems of the body in their entirety. A particular interest is the definition of acceptable loads and the dynamics of mental work capacity in the context of increasing and complicating educational loads.

In this regard, the issue of a schoolchild’s educational load currently attracts more attention not only from educators and doctors but also from the general public, requiring the unification of their efforts to prevent the overload of schoolchildren with educational activities, which could lead to chronic overwork and serious deviations from the normal health of children.

The issues of safeguarding the health of the younger generation, including the prevention of student fatigue and related to the prevention of educational overloads in schoolchildren, should be at the forefront of the attention of the medical-pedagogical team of schools and the parent community.

Researchers point to the necessity of eliminating the overload of schoolchildren, and schools are tasked with caring for the physical development and strengthening of students' health. Based on this, questions regarding the establishment of optimal standards for educational loads on schoolchildren remain highly relevant. These standards should, on the one hand, provide conditions for students to acquire the knowledge set out in the curriculum, and on the other hand, allow enough time for extracurricular activities and hobbies, and finally, ensure that this does not negatively affect the students' health, physical development, and work capacity.

Methodology. The study of pedagogical and hygienic aspects of educational loads, as well as ways to prevent educational overloads, is one of the pressing problems for the medical-pedagogical teams of schools.

The necessity of obtaining such information arises from contradictory opinions regarding educational loads. Some scholars believe that educational loads in modern schools cannot lead to overloads and overwork in schoolchildren. Parents and teachers, when noticing changes in the well-being and behavior of a student, do not always give them due attention, especially if they are temporary and not distinctly expressed.

It should be noted that the genesis of mental fatigue in school-aged children, the physiological nature of this process, and ways to eliminate it are among the difficult and least

developed issues in the physiology of a healthy child. Indeed, due to the transition to a new educational content, pediatricians and especially school doctors have to constantly observe a range of diseases among students of general education schools, which are undoubtedly associated with excessive overload of children due to intense mental work. The results of this overstrain manifest in a number of disorders of higher nervous activity, phases of the large hemispheres, headaches, irritability, or conversely, sluggishness, decreased attention, memory, and loss of appetite.

Definitely, as mental fatigue increases, the work performed by the child becomes increasingly uneven and unproductive. There arises uncertainty in the accuracy of perceiving external impressions, and what is being learned is not accurately remembered. This becomes especially noticeable when a child is asked to read a section of text and then retell what has been read.

Often, the increase in mental fatigue in children aged 13-15 is manifested in an irresistible desire to stop working. They complain of general malaise. As fatigue continues to increase, children cease to perceive what is necessary to correctly complete homework in subjects such as mathematics, physics, etc., lose the logical connection between thoughts, their memory weakens significantly, and they have to reread the text several times. Drowsiness, sometimes headaches, and other unpleasant sensations may appear.

Physical signs of mental fatigue include paleness of the skin and mucous membranes, relaxation, slouching posture, sluggishness, lack of confidence in movement, and sometimes hand tremors.

Psychological symptoms become clearly evident due to disturbances in the nervous system: slowing down the pace of work, an increase in the number of mistakes, the appearance of gloom, apathy, irritability, and moodiness in the child. Both physical and mental work capacity decrease. Specific psychological symptoms of mental fatigue in children include impaired attention, weakened memory, disruption of logical structures, imagination, and the ability for abstraction.

Results and discussion. Moreover, when overloaded with school activities, healthy children exhibit certain elements of a neurasthenic condition: sleep disorders, decreased performance, and headaches. Constant mental fatigue, lack of fresh air, sleep, rest, and psychological trauma undoubtedly lead to psychological activation and reduced resistance to colds and other diseases in children who were previously healthy.

While studying indicators of mental performance throughout the day, it is possible to highlight specific periods and build a curve of performance, which is the most objective criterion for establishing a rational schedule for the school and working day.

The curve of mental performance includes 5 main periods:

1. **Period of Adaptation:** The duration of this period ranges from several minutes (during a lesson) to an hour (at the workplace), and it is characterized by a gradual increase in performance, mood, and adaptation to specific environmental conditions. During this period, a functional dominance of the nerve centers that regulate the functions required to perform the task is formed.
2. **Period of Optimal Performance:** This period is characterized by stable mental performance. The functional state of a person is determined by a "stable working state." During this period, all changes in the indicators of the body's functions are proportional to the load the person is experiencing and fluctuate within physiological norms.

However, period of Full Compensation: The period of optimal performance gradually and imperceptibly transitions into the period of full compensation. A distinctive feature of this period is the emergence of initial signs of fatigue, which, however, are compensated by the person's willpower, but are accompanied by significant shifts in vegetative functions.

Period of Unstable Compensation: This period is characterized by increasing fatigue, i.e., a decrease in performance, but the person can still maintain mental performance at the required level for some time through willpower. The degree of reduction in performance and the ability to compensate for it during this period depend significantly on individual characteristics, the type of nervous system, physical training, and the range of compensatory capabilities.

Moreover, period of Progressive Decrease in Performance: This period is characterized by rapid accumulation of fatigue, which manifests in decreased productivity, reduced efficiency of mental work, and functional shifts that are inadequate to the task being performed. During this period, a person is no longer able to compensate for the decrease in performance through willpower. Before the end of the work, a so-called "final surge" can be observed, which is characterized by a brief increase in work efficiency. [1,2]

Similar performance curves can be traced throughout the duration of a lesson, day, week, term, or year.

Mental performance can change depending on the student's well-being and mood, their understanding of the task at hand, interest in it, emotions, and willpower. With increased academic workloads, prolonged and quite intense work, mental fatigue sets in. During mental fatigue, memory strength decreases, which leads to the "flight of thoughts," the rapid disappearance of information that was learned not long before.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that while changing the volume of mental workloads, it is necessary to consider the dynamics of mental performance, which can respond at any stage of the performance curve.

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